

HRM practices and post-promotion managerial performance - subordinates' perspective

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Abstract

Purpose- The purpose of the study is to investigate the relationship between human resource management practices and post-promotion performance of managers from subordinates' perspective.

Design/methodology/approach- For the study, survey methodology was used and 391 respondents who fulfilled selection criteria set for the study responded. The hypothesized relationships were examined by regression analysis.

Findings- It was found that the job description and promotion practices have significant relationship with post-promotion performance.

Practical implications- The findings imply the importance of promotion practices and the need of maintaining and using job descriptions in facilitating post-promotion performance.

Originality/value- Several previous studies investigated the post-promotion managerial performance based on mathematical modelling and single firm case studies. However, it is very rare to find academic research that investigated the relationship between human resource management practices and post-promotion performance of managers.

Key words Human resource management, human resource management practices, job performance, promotion.

Paper type Research Paper

Introduction

Business organisations world-wide use promotions to assign employees to a higher level job positions where they can best contribute to organisations' performance. Promoted employees may experience an increase in earnings and they may receive opportunities to acquire new capabilities while organisations will be able to retain their valuable employees (Cobb-Clark and Dunlop, 1999).

However, previous studies (such as Anderson et al., 1999; Fairburn and Malcomson, 2001; Lazear, 2004) provide evidence that employees' post-promotion performance falls relative to his or her pre-promotion performance. Further, previous studies (e.g., Baker et al., 1994; Chan, 2006) provide evidence that when competing with the external labour market, potential new hires have an advantage over incumbents for the higher level job positions. In a similar vein, it could be assumed that when competing within the internal labour market, there may be a ceiling for an internal employee once a certain level of hierarchy is reached. These situations challenge the conventional view that firm specific human capital is rare and valuable, and has implications for the career advancement of employees within the firm.

Therefore, research into human resource management (HRM) practices and post-promotion performance of managers are important for several reasons. First, the majority of previous studies on post-promotion performance were based on mathematical modelling (e.g., Fairburn and Malcomson, 2001; Lazear, 2004) or single firm case studies (e.g., Barmby et al., 2012) using secondary data. The findings of such studies do not provide sufficient information to make informed decisions across organisations. Hence, more studies are needed to provide new, rare evidence in order to enhance the understanding of post-promotion performance. As detailed in the section on *sample*, we have attempted to overcome this shortcoming by conducting an empirical study in Sri Lanka.

Second, our extensive review of academic journals in management failed to find specific empirical studies that investigated the relationship between HRM practices and post-promotion performance of managers. Therefore, building on the available literature on post-promotion performance of managers, there is a room to question what is the relationship between HRM practices and post-promotion performance of managers?

In the above context, the main objective of our study was to investigate the relationship between HRM practices and post-promotion managerial performance. The literature identifies subordinates' feedback as one of the main sources of 360-degree or multi-source performance feedback programmes (Atkins and Wood, 2002; Brutus et al., 1999; DeNisi and Kluger, 2000; Kets de Vries et al., 2004) and subordinates' ratings serve as a basis for subsequent selection of development goals of managers (Brutus et al., 1999; Kets de Vries et al., 2004). Building on such literature, the study investigated the subordinates' perspective on post-promotion performance of their immediate superiors.

Consistent with the objectives, in the next section, relevant literature is briefly reviewed. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Subsequently, the main findings are presented and discussed. The paper concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Review of literature

Promotion

There is an agreement on the meaning of the term "promotion" in the HRM literature (Iverson and Roy, 1994; Peters et al., 2000; Spilerman and Lunde, 1991). Peters et al. (2000, p. 274) define promotion as "the advancement of an individual from a particular position to one higher rank within the organisational hierarchy". A promotion is almost always

associated with the increases in responsibility, salary and organisational benefits (Peters et al., 2000).

These features of promotion distinguish it from job changes due to lateral transfers such as scheduled non-merit upgrades, task reorganisations or job reclassifications, which are not necessarily merit driven, usually do not involve substantial changes in the compensation, and do not imply career advancement (Acosta, 2010; Schaefer et al., 1979).

Post-promotion performance

Peter and Hull (1969, p. 27) said “assuming the existence of enough ranks in the hierarchy - each employee rises to, and remains at, his or her level of incompetence”; this situation may be applicable to all employees in all organisational hierarchies. Fetzer (2006) showed that an employee climbs up the ladder until he or she reaches a level within the organisation in which he or she cannot perform competently, and the duties of the new job are too much for he or she to handle well. Dwan (2000, p.72) states “for various reasons a manager may struggle to function in he or she role. ... poor performance is (will be) the norm. ... staff carrying or covering for an incompetent manager eventually get to a point when they have had enough. Tolerance will evaporate, replaced by a loss of job satisfaction, reduced personal performance and a lack of commitment to their role and the organisation. At which point, experienced staff may decide to leave”. Further, based on a case study conducted in a large hierarchical British financial sector firm, Barmby et al. (2012) provide evidence that managers’ performance decline after promotion. In addition, several researchers based on mathematical modelling (e.g. Dickinson and Villeval, 2012; Fairburn and Malcomson, 2001; Lazear, 2004) and secondary data obtained from single firm case studies (e.g. Anderson et al., 1999; Barmby et al., 2012; Fetzer, 2006) showed that managers’ post-promotion performance decline, on average, relative to their pre-promotion performance.

Human resource management practices as predictors of post-promotion performance

Becker and Huselid (2010, p. 391) state “the most common empirical specification in the strategic HRM (SHRM) literature is a regression of a measure of business performance on an additive index of HRM practices”. According to Becker and Huselid (2010), a system of HRM practices emphasizes the dimensions thought to influence workforce performance. For instance, a system of HRM practices should have a clear relationship between employee selection, development and performance. The SHRM literature also posits the need of identifying a combination of practices that are effective in creating competitive advantage rather than the effects of single HRM practices (Barney and Wright, 1998; Becker and Huselid, 2010). According to Becker and Huselid (2010), a combination of HRM practices can be identified as a strategic resource creating competitive advantage when these are not only valuable, but also inimitable.

Yet, the literature provides evidence for non-conclusive effects of HRM practices for the career advancement of employees within the firm. On the one hand, when considering the internal labour market, the literature suggests that performance-contingent rewards on employees’ behaviour (such as promotions) and incentives can influence shirking (Becker and Huselid, 1992). For instance, the tournament theory (Lazear and Rosen, 1981) suggests that internal promotion competitions motivate employees to devote greater attention to organizational interests at all job levels discouraging shirking (Becker and Huselid, 1992). The motivation crowding effect (Frey, 1997) suggests that an external intervention through monetary incentives or punishments may not always yield expected outcomes. However, despite the theoretical appeal of these standings among economists (e.g., Frey, 1997) and psychologists (e.g., Deci, 1975), the practical relevance of these as explanations for

promotions remains an open empirical question (DeVaro, 2006) with implications for HRM practices on the career advancement of employees within the firm.

On the other hand, when comparing the internal labour market with external labour market, Lazear (2004) showed that employees who were promoted do not appear to be as able as they were before the promotion (p. S159). Hence, Lazear (2004) concluded “in a multilevel firm, the typical worker who remains at a given level is not as good as the average worker coming into the job, nor is he or she as good as he or she was in his or her previous assignment relative to the comparison set” (p. S160). In a similar vein, Acosta (2010) suggests that the ability of a promoted manager could be less compared to his or her pool of new co-workers. Further, some studies (e.g. Acosta, 2010; Baker et al., 1994; Chan, 2006) provide evidence that potential job seekers from the external labour market have an advantage when competing with equivalent incumbents for a higher job position even though they have less firm-specific human capital than incumbents. However, Baker et al. (1994) provide evidence that although new hires are initially promoted more quickly than incumbents they do not have further advantage over incumbents in the subsequent competitions for promotions in the firm. Schaefer et al. (1979) compared the loss of innovation once the employee is not producing enough to cover the cost of his or her wage, and proposed the importance of rotating the employee across job positions to allow him or her to continue to innovate and to ensure that the value of his or her contributions exceed his or her wage. Such issues in the post-promotion performance may have occurred due to various reasons such as reduced incentives (Barnby et al., 2012), the strategic behaviour of employees who outperform prior to the promotion and tend to relax or return to their natural levels of performance thereafter (Acosta, 2010) and due to the fair wage-effort hypothesis (Akerlof & Yellen, 1990). However, on the contrary, some previous studies provide evidence for the existence of “fast track” in promotions, where the fast track career path is identified as

those who were promoted quickly at one level were promoted quickly at the next level suggesting the lack of importance of seniority for continual success in careers in the firm (e.g., Baker et al., 1994; Bernhardt, 1995; Gibbons and Waldman, 1999). The findings of these studies also emphasize the importance of empirical investigations on the effects of HRM practices on the career advancement of employees within the firm.

In the above context, the present study investigated the effects of HRM practices in terms of promotion practices, job analysis, performance management, and human resource development on the post-promotion managerial performance. Hence, following sections review in brief the literature within the scope of the present study.

Performance management practices

Lazear (2004, S141) states “being promoted is evidence that a standard has been met”. In this regard, Popper and Gluskinos (1993, p. 63) suggest “in practice, the inverse will rarely happen since promotion is usually based on previous success”. Hence, past performance can be considered as a predictor of future performance since past performance signals an individual’s ability to drive his or her continued success in the career (Longenecker and Fink, 2008; Lyness and Heilman, 2006; Powell and Butterfield, 1994; Silzer and Church, 2009). Therefore, an individual who performed best in the current job merits a promotion (Silzer and Church, 2009).

Previous studies investigated the importance of performance management practices in evaluating employees’ performance and making decisions on future promotions (e.g., Breaugh, 2011; Lyness and Heilman, 2006; Powell and Butterfield, 1994; Gorjup et al., 2008). For instance, Powell and Butterfield (1994), Lyness and Heilman (2006) and Breaugh (2011) found a positive significant relationship between past performance and who gets promoted. Gorjup et al. (2008) provide evidence for a significant positive relationship

between continuous daily supervision and the control of job tasks of subordinates and the usage of this information in promotion decisions.

Some studies suggest the importance of promotability ratings in making better promotion decisions (e.g., de Pater et al., 2009; Garman and Glawe, 2004). Effective performance management system not only captures the individuals' details of past performance but also about the potential. For instance, the studies of Breugh (2011), de Pater et al. (2009) and Shore et al. (2003) provide a positive correlation between performance ratings and promotability ratings. Some studies provide evidence for a positive correlation between promotability ratings and actual promotions (e.g. Breugh, 2011; Powell and Butterfield, 1994).

With regard to performance management practices and post-promotion performance, our rigorous review of literature led to identify only one study (i.e., Dickinson and Villeval, 2012) that commented on performance management practices and post-promotion performance. Based on the findings of this study, Dickinson and Villeval (2012) commented that the imperfect appraisal of transitory ability could influence effort distortions in post-promotion performance.

Based on the literature reviewed above, it is evident that performance appraisal information can be used when making decisions on future promotions since it is capable of capturing individuals potential (Breugh, 2011; de Pater et al., 2009; Garman and Glawe, 2004; Shore et al., 2003). Therefore, we consider well-designed performance management practices as practices that not only capture individuals' past performance but also the potential. Building on the literature reviewed above, it is predicted that the existence of well-designed performance management practices foster post-promotion managerial performance. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H1: Well-designed performance management practices foster post-promotion managerial performance.

Job design and analysis

The dimensionality of a job and work design is important in making decisions by individuals as well as organizations. The design of a job describes the structure, content, and configuration of a person's work tasks, roles and work environment (Erez, 2010). The early scholarly work on job design focused on bringing greater control and efficiency to the workplace by designing work systems with standardized operations and highly simplified work (Taylor, 1911). Herzberg (1976) provide a valuable point of departure by claiming that jobs should be designed and managed to foster responsibility, achievement, growth, recognition, and advancement. The work of Hackman and Oldham (1976) concentrated on identifying the characteristics of jobs that foster a state of internal work motivation to perform jobs. Recently, researchers have extended Hackman and Oldham's (1976) theory with newly added job characteristics (refer to Foss et al., 2009). The design of a job has an immediate influence on an individual's perception as facilitating or inhibiting opportunities for being successful and for experiencing self-worth and well-being (Erez, 2010, p. 389).

Peters et al. (2000, p. 181) define job analysis as "the systematic process of uncovering and describing the components of a job. ... the job analyst may explore the goals of work, work procedures and processes (duties, tasks, and so forth), the kinds of personal attributes required of people to complete the work, and the work context, broadly defined to include the physical environment as well as the business environment". Hence, job analysis identifies job tasks and work behaviours required for successful job performance. Job descriptions are derived from the job analysis (Armstrong, 2003, p. 192). Several HRM practices such as human resource planning, employee resourcing, training, and rewards

management use the information provided by job analysis in managing human resources of the firm (Peters et al., 2000). For instance, Peters et al. (2000, p. 182) state “among the vast uses of job analysis are producing a written description of the nature of the job (a job description), providing information used to set salaries and planning for the future of people at work in the organisation (human resource planning). Job analysis also forms the basis for training programmes, hiring and promoting workers, defending the job-relatedness of employment practices and defining the job in such a way that job performance can be evaluated”.

As discussed earlier, some previous studies suggest that individuals who got promoted to a higher level in the hierarchy may not perform well in the new job position compared to the previous job position (e.g., Fairburn and Malcomson, 2001; Fetzer, 2006; Lazear, 2004; Pluchino et al., 2010). For instance, Fairburn and Malcomson (2001) state that when a firm promotes an individual who had performed well in the (present) job to a higher hierarchical level, he or she may simply be transferred to a job to which he or she is not well suited. Similarly Lazear (2004, p. S143) states “individuals who are good in one job are not necessarily good in the job into which they are promoted. As a result, individuals appear incompetent in the job in which they settle”. Fetzer (2006) and King (2004) found that when individuals climb up the organisational ladder, he or she will be promoted to a job position into which job duties are too much for this person to handle well. In this regard, some studies showed the importance of information availability about the nature of the job and the requirements of individuals to perform the job when making promotion decisions (e.g., Bayo-Moriones and Ortin-Angel, 2006, Breaugh, 2011; Silzer and Church, 2009). Bayo-Moriones and Ortin-Angel (2006) showed the importance of information availability about skills and competences of employees in making promotion decisions. Silzer and Church (2009) highlighted the importance of analysing how similar the present and higher-level jobs are

when making promotion decisions. Breugh (2011) highlighted the importance of analysing how hard an employee had to work to perform well. Overall, these studies emphasise the importance of job analysis in providing a true picture of the job context and job demands to develop proper job descriptions for each job. Therefore, within the scope of the present study, it is predicted that the existence of up-to-date job descriptions foster post-promotion managerial performance. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H2: Job descriptions foster post-promotion managerial performance.

Human resource development

Human resource development (HRD) is a conscious endeavour within an organisation to translate learning processes to meet present and future organisational requirements. Hence, organizations should plan its HRD interventions based on human resource plans. In this regard, Rimler (1971, p. 37) states “training must recognize that the skills necessary in previous positions are not necessarily needed for success in future positions; in fact, they may well be a detriment”. In a recent study, Heilmann (2011) states that the continuous development of skills and knowledge enables employees to make their career decisions while identifying further training needs. Previous studies also showed that plateauing has a relation to learning and development of employees (e.g., Allen et al., 1999; Cann and Cangemi, 1971; Patz, 1975). These studies suggest that organisations use a combination of HRD interventions that address different elements of HRD to prepare employees to meet present and future organisational requirements while extending the scope of organisational capabilities (Heilmann, 2011; Liao et al., 2011). In this regard, the literature identifies HRD as a mean of developing competitive advantage (e.g., Castellanos and Martín, 2011).

The present study concentrates on the performance of individuals in managerial job positions. In this context, Heilmann (2011) states that historically, training has meant formal

training, which is planned in advance in a structured format. Organisations that views employee development as an investment provide various forms of on-the-job (such as job rotation, apprenticeships, understudy assignments and formal mentoring programmes) and off-the-job training programmes (such as live classroom lectures, public seminars, self-study programmes, online courses, satellite-beamed television classes, group activities that use role-plays, and computer-based or e-training) (Liao et al., 2011; Heilmann, 2011; Ng and Dastmalchian, 2011). Further, Allen et al. (1999, p. 1116) state “employees with a proclivity toward the development of new skills and abilities and who work in environments that are conducive to those activities are less likely to experience a career plateau since their personal growth is continually being developed”.

When reviewing the literature on HRD interventions and promotions, previous research provides evidence for a positive relationship between the provision of HRD interventions and probability of being promoted (Bayo-Moriones and Ortin-Angel, 2006; Cobb-Clark and Dunlop, 1999; Gorjup et al., 2008). For instance, Cobb-Clark and Dunlop (1999) and Bayo-Moriones and Ortin-Angel (2006) found that firms’ investment in enhancing specific skills, knowledge and exposure in employees is positively related to the probability of being promoted. However, Gorjup et al. (2008) did not find such a significant relationship between training and promotion in their study on call centres. Although the literature reviewed above suggests the importance of a combination of various HRD interventions to foster the post-promotion performance of individuals in managerial job positions, the present study mainly investigated the HRM function led formal HRD interventions. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H3: HRM function led formal HRD interventions foster post-promotion managerial performance.

Promotion practices

The aim of promotion practices is to enable an organisation to obtain the best talent available to fill more senior job positions and provide employees with opportunities to advance in their careers within the organisation (Armstrong, 2003, p. 859). An employee may receive a promotion based on, on the one hand, formal criteria such as merits in past performance and/or seniority, where a merit-based promotion system serves as an incentive for motivating him or her to appropriate levels of effort and performance (DeVaro, 2006). On the other hand, an employee may receive a promotion based on informal criteria such as personal influences, political influences, personal liking and the imperfect appraisal of transitory ability which leads to bias in the promotion process (Acosta, 2010; Breugh, 2011; Dickinson and Villeval, 2012). The works of Breugh (2011) and Dickinson and Villeval (2012) imply the importance of well-designed promotion practices to foster post-promotion performance.

In this regard, Armstrong (2003, p. 859) states “it is advisable to have a promotion policy and procedure ... and this procedure should take full account of equal opportunity policies”. According to Armstrong (2003), appropriate promotion practices include internal vacancy notification and the opening of promotion opportunities to all irrespective of race, creed, sex or marital status. Some studies highlighted the importance of having knowledge about the capabilities of employees in making promotion decisions (Bayo-Moriones and Ortin-Angel, 2006; Gorjup et al., 2008; Popper and Gluskinos, 1993). For instance, Gorjup et al. (2008) found a positive significant relationship between firm’s knowledge about the skills of employees and its use in promotions. Popper and Gluskinos (1993) identified the importance of raising the question of to what extent individuals can progress from one level to the next and acquire the necessary competences in making managerial selection and promotion decisions.

The literature emphasises the importance of appropriate promotion practices in fostering post-promotion performance (Baker et al., 1994; Buchman, 2010; Dickinson and Villeval, 2012; Fairburn and Malcolmson, 2001; Lazear, 2004; Pluchino et al., 2010). First, the literature on labour economics provides evidence that firms use promotion as an incentive (Baker et al., 1994; Dickinson and Villeval, 2012; Fairburn and Malcolmson, 2001). The use of promotion as an incentive may lead to decrease post-promotion performance when employees are promoted to jobs for which they are not necessarily well suited (Baker et al., 1988; Fairburn and Malcolmson, 2001).

Second, several previous studies provide evidence for the use of inappropriate promotion practices (e.g., Acosta, 2010; Beeman, 1981; Breugh, 2011). Acosta (2010) suggests that promotion decisions could be taken based on criteria other than performance such as loyalty, influence, favouritism, personal relationships, creating an equal-opportunity environment, or even by overvaluing unfamiliar candidates (external labour market) and undervaluing known ones (internal labour market). Breugh (2011) states that bias may enter into promotability rating process since the perceptions of an employee's capabilities held by appraisers could influence their decisions. According to Peter (1969), an employee's superior will evaluate him or her in terms of actual output only if the superior is still at the level of competence. Beeman (1981) states that it is organisational politics that promotes employees and not competence. Hence, these previous studies suggest that in an environment of inappropriate promotion practices, promotions may not be based solely on performance (Dickinson and Villeval, 2012) and bias may enter into promotion decisions (Beeman, 1981; Breugh, 2011). As a consequence, such promotion practices may not serve organisational objectives (e.g., Beeman, 1981; Breugh, 2011). For instance, Breugh (2011, p. 264) compared the consequences of appropriate and inappropriate promotion practices and stated "a well-designed process for deciding which employees get promoted can result in talent

flowing to the highest levels of an organisation where decisions are likely to have the greatest impact. In contrast, if wrongly passed over for promotion, talented individuals may resign or become less motivated". Therefore, we consider well-designed promotion practices as practices that enable to obtain the best talent available in the organisation to fill job vacancies and to provide opportunities for employees to advance in their careers within the organisation. Based on the literature reviewed above that emphasises the importance of appropriate promotion practices to foster post-promotion managerial performance, it is hypothesised:

H4: Well-designed promotion practices foster post-promotion managerial performance.

Methodology

Measures

Post-promotion performance was measured by 7 items developed for the study to identify subordinates' perceptions of performance of their immediate managers. Building on Ott and Shafritz (1994), respondents evaluated their immediate superior's possession of sufficient and suitable (adequate but may not be exceptional) skills, knowledge and experience to accomplish aims of the job role.

Human resource management practices were measured by 13 items developed for the study since we have not come across previous studies that have slight resemblance to our study. These items measures were developed building on insight gained from the previous studies on performance management (such as de Pater et al., 2009; DeNisi and Kluger, 2000; Gorjup et al., 2008; Lyness and Heilman, 2006), promotion practices (such as Bayo-Moriones and Ortin-Angel, 2006; Breugh, 2011; Dickinson and Villeval, 2012), HRD interventions (such as Heilmann, 2011; Liao et al., 2011; Ng and Dastmalchian, 2011), and job description

(such as Armstrong, 2003; Erez, 2010; Foss et al., 2009). This 13-item measure assessed the extent to which these four HRM practices were adhered to by the firms from the perspective of subordinates to achieve the specific objectives of our study.

Sample and method of data collection

The study was conducted in the software development sector in Sri Lanka. The preliminary investigations made by us led to identify 15 software development firms with more than 10 years of industry presence and these were considered as the sample of the study. This restriction on the years of industry presence (or business existence) was imposed to eliminate firms where specific HRM practices are not explicit. Of these firms, four firms had over 300 employees, six firms had 300 to 100 employees while five firms had less than 100 employees. A contact person was identified at each firm to distribute the survey questionnaire.

Building on the literature reviewed earlier that emphasizes the value of subordinates' feedback in 360-degree performance feedback programmes (such as Atkins and Wood, 2002; Brutus et al., 1999; DeNisi and Kluger, 2000; Kets de Vries et al., 2004) we designed our study to examine subordinates perceptions of post-promotion performance of their immediate managers. It was decided to collect data from subordinates whose immediate manager had been promoted to the present position at least 18 months ago from the time of data collection. In this regard, SLICTA (2013) provides evidence that the average tenure expected of new recruits in non-managerial positions, in almost every job category, is to stay for at least two years in a particular firm from the day they start. Therefore, this study was not designed to collect data from subordinates about their immediate supervisors' pre-promotion performance. Accordingly, none of the items used to operationalize post-promotion performance involve comparing superior's current performance with the past performance.

The anonymity of the respondents was ensured to reduce evaluation apprehension. 391 valid responses were yielded. Respondents were from the lower and middle levels of the organisational hierarchy in the respective software development firms; they held job positions such as technical leads, quality assurance leads, project managers, and software architects.

With regard to the demographic characteristics of respondents, we collected data on age, sex, the highest level of education and the tenure of respondents and the number of employees of the firms to which these respondents belonged to. Accordingly, 55% were male and 45% were female. All the respondents belonged to the age range of 23 to 48 years (mean = 28). 88% of the respondents had Bachelor's degrees or equivalent qualifications and 12% had postgraduate degrees as the highest level of education. 42% employed in firms with less than 150 full-time employees, 58% attached to firms with 150 to 300 full-time employees. The mean tenure in the IT industry was four years (S.D. = 2.64, Maximum = 20), mean tenure in the present workplace was two and half years (S.D. = 1.89, Maximum = 17), and mean tenure in the present job position was 1.94 (S.D. = 0.64, Maximum = 7).

Methods of data analysis

For all Likert scaled variables, standardized Cronbach's alpha was examined; principal component factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7. Harman's single-factor test was conducted to assess common method variance; neither single factor emerged from this analysis nor was there a general factor that could account for the majority of variance.

In preparing data for the analysis, composite mean was taken when more than one subordinate rated the same supervisor's post-promotion performance. The variables were

mean centred to increase interpretability of results. The items of each factor derived from factor analysis were averaged to produce a mean score for the each construct. Data of the four predictor variables were tested for collinearity using structure matrix, testing for equality of group means and calculating standardized coefficients.

As detailed earlier, the respondents for the study came from 15 firms. When 391 respondents are nested within 15 firms, this clustering has implications for the assumption of independence of observations. When selecting the sample, we randomly selected a cross-section of employees covering 10 per cent of the total number of employees from each firm. Although this restriction was imposed due to the time and cost constraints of administering the questionnaire, the procedure we adopted avoided getting a relatively skewed distribution of respondents per firm. Further, SLICTA (2013) suggests that firms tend to be fairly similar and post-promotion performance of managers from subordinates' perspective has little to do with geography or the workplace itself suggesting that the effect of firm may be negligible. Yet, we assessed the extent to which firm cluster explains variance in the outcome variable using SPSS "mixed" procedure (refer to IBM-SPSS Statistics, 2012a). The results yielded for type III tests of fixed effects and estimates of fixed effects confirmed that the contribution of each firm on the outcome variable is not significant ($p > .05$).

Considering the ordinal nature of data obtained in the study to evaluate the variables, ordinal logit regression was used to test the hypotheses. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve was created and estimated the area under the curve to evaluate the performance of classification schemes in logit regression.

Results and discussion

The 7-item measure on post-promotion performance was subjected to reliability analysis. The measure had a Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.933. Factor analysis was conducted to

identify the underlying dimensions as perceived by respondents. Table 1 summarises the results of factor analysis. Factor analysis yielded one factor, which explained 72% of the variance.

Take in Table 1

The 13-item measure on HRM practices had a Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.889. Factor analysis yielded four factors, which explained 80% of the variance. The item measures, factor loadings and reliability statistics are shown in Table 2.

Take in Table 2

Zero-order correlations between the variables are shown in Table 3. To assess any issues of multi-collinearity between four predictors on the Likert scales, we tested for standardized coefficients, the equality of group means, and structure matrix (refer to IBM-SPSS Statistics, 2012b). The results are shown in Appendix 1. The ordering of the predictors in the structure matrix was the same as the order suggested by the tests of equality of group means and standardized coefficients table. This suggests that there are no issues with multi-collinearity between the four predictors. As can be seen in Table 3, correlations between post-promotion performance and job description and promotion practices are high and significant suggesting better prediction in the subsequent analysis.

Take in Table 3

The non-significance chi-square value of 303.715 of Pearson statistic and 264.56 of deviance statistic suggested a good fit. The -2 Log-likelihood value was 278.567 ($p < .001$). The results of the regression analysis are summarised in Table 4. Standard error values of the variables ranged from .06 to .341. Parameter estimates suggest that the contribution of each HRM practice is significant. That is, job description had the highest effect followed by promotion practices. To provide the visual index of the accuracy of results, we created ROC curve for the four predictors and estimated the area under the curve to evaluate the performance of classification schemes in logit regression. Figure 1 shows ROC curve with four curves of the four predictors plotted with the reference line. The numerical summary of ROC curve for the four predictors given in Appendix 2 confirms that the classification scheme of logit regression is accurate since all the four curves lay above the reference line (refer to IBM-SPSS Statistics, 2012c). Overall, the results of the analysis given in Table 4 support all the four hypotheses set for the study.

Take in Table 4

Take in Figure 1

Conclusions and implications

Although the literature emphasises the importance of post-promotion managerial performance, empirical studies linking HRM practices and post-promotion performance of managers are very limited. Based on a sample from software development firms in Sri Lanka, we investigated the effect of HRM practices on post-promotion managerial performance from subordinates' point of view. Analysis yielded single component factor structures for post-

promotion managerial performance whereas four component factor structure for HRM practices. The four HRM practices of performance management, job analysis, human resource development, and promotion practices are significant in fostering post-promotion managerial performance. Of these four HRM practices, job analysis had the highest individual effect followed by promotion practices.

With regard to job analysis, the findings suggest the importance of having information about jobs and taking such information granted in making promotion decisions. Promotions are linked to increased responsibilities and changes in work duties. Therefore, findings imply that the promotion decisions should be taken with the consideration of job description information such as the goals of work, work procedures and processes, the personal attributes required of employees to complete the work and the work context of employees to be promoted to jobs for which they are well-suited. Such mechanisms will foster post-promotion performance. With regard to promotion practices, the findings suggest the importance of following standard procedures and making correct decisions based on objective data when making promotion decisions. We found that well-designed promotion practices foster post-promotion performance. The findings also support the importance of performance management and HRM function led formal HRD interventions as practices fostering post-promotion performance. With regard to performance management practices, the findings suggest the importance of obtaining, analyzing, and recording information on performance of employees. Previous research (e.g. Breugh, 2011; de Pater et al., 2009; Shore et al., 2003) empirically showed the importance of performance ratings in making decisions about an employee's potential. With regard to HRD interventions, findings suggests the importance of HRM function led formal HRD interventions that are centred on incumbents' possible future job postings in fostering post-promotion performance.

The findings of our study have important implications for the theory and practice. With regard to the contribution of the study for the literature, as discussed earlier, there are several studies that emphasised the importance of investigating causes and consequences of post-promotion performance in the literature on labour economics. However, there is surprisingly little empirical research addressing links between HRM practices and post-promotion performance in the literature. There are few practitioner papers (e.g., Rimler, 1971) suggesting the contribution of HRD in fostering post-promotion performance; some studies (e.g., Cann and Cangemi, 1971; Patz, 1975) investigated the effect of HRD using mathematical modelling while several other studies (e.g., Breugh, 2011; Gorjup et al., 2008) investigated the relationship between performance management and the probability of getting promoted (but not on post-promotion performance). Some previous studies (e.g. Lazear, 2004) showed the possibilities of a decrease in an individual's performance after receiving a promotion and concluded this as an ever-present phenomenon in organisations and it is not an occurrence due to misalignment in promotion process or mistakes in promotion decisions. In this context, the present study made a contribution to the literature by investigating effects of several HRM practices on post-promotion managerial performance in a single empirical study using quantitative research methodology. Therefore, we believe that the findings of our study provide baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

With regard to the contribution of the study for practice, first, the findings imply that promotion and succession policies and processes organisations use to make promotion decisions could make a significant effect on managers' post-promotion performance. Second, on the one hand, job descriptions provides information needed by appraisers in selection and promotion panels to make promotion decisions. On the other hand, individuals who aspire to ascend the organisational hierarchy must have the desire to do more than fulfilling the job

roles in the present job, and should search for information from job analysis to self-develop the needed capabilities at the next level. Third, especially, in the software development sector a decisive success factor for software firms is the quality of software produced. The attainment of this objective largely depends on the calibre of employees. However, several industry reports showed that the success rate of information technology projects range from 16% to 24% (e.g., Ambler, 2011; Bloch et al., 2012). These practitioner reports reveal that main failures in IT projects were due to issues such as unrealistic estimations, poor quality products, unnecessary reworks and the lack of proper leadership (Cline et al., 1998). Cline et al. (1998) identified this situation as over promoting and the under development of technical specialists. The trend in software sector is to promote a software developer who demonstrates high capabilities in the present job to a managerial position, in which the individual may have little opportunity to perform the original technical tasks that gained him or her acclaim (Cline et al., 1998). Another trend in the software sector is to promote a software engineer to senior software engineer based on present job performance. However, the individual may lack the necessary capabilities to cope with the new responsibilities assigned to him or her (Cline et al., 1998). For instance, software engineer may not be required to engage in software designing, but once he or she becomes a senior software engineer, his or her new responsibilities may require engaging in software designing as well. In this regard, in the contemporary business world, individual development is mainly self-development. Therefore, future research should look into other elements of management development discussed above.

Limitations of the study and areas for future research

This research was designed as a cross-sectional study employing survey methodology. First, to assess the effect of firm cluster on the outcome variable we used SPSS “mixed” procedure

and results suggested that the effect of firm is not significant. Future research could verify this by using SAS or Stata using clustered robust standard errors and multilevel modelling. By doing so, future researchers will be able to compare the results of point estimates and standard errors generated by above methods to enhance our understanding on cluster effects. Second, the study relied on subjective evaluation by subordinates about their immediate superior. Future research could correlate secondary data (such as supervisors' post-promotion length of tenure and firm turnover) and primary data (such as subordinates rating on supervisors' post-promotion performance). Firms in our sample refused to provide performance data (such as profits and turnover) which could influence the level of practices adopted. Since none of the firms were listed in Colombo Stock Exchange (or any other stock exchange) we have not had any other mean to access their annual reports to obtain data. The incorporation of such data as contextual variables in future research could enhance the understanding of the relationships proposed in the study.

Third, the literature on economics and psychology give a prominent place to the effect of performance-contingent rewards on behaviour such as promotions as an incentive mechanism. On the one hand, the tournament theory explains internal promotion competitions where internal employees compete for promotions and the winning prize is the difference in wages between post-promotion and pre-promotion (Lazear and Rosen, 1981). On the other hand, motivation crowding effect suggests that external interventions via monetary incentives or punishments may undermine intrinsic motivation (Deci, 1975; Frey, 1997). Investigating these aspects is beyond the scope of the present study. Fourth, future research could investigate problems faced by the HRM function when dealing with managers suffering from post-promotion performance to find remedies from that end.

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Tables

Tables 1. Summary of results: factor analysis - post-promotion managerial performance

	Factor loading
My manager ignores his/her duties and focus more on activities that are not direct responsibilities of his/her position	.880
My manager shifts the blame on to others for his/her own actions	.872
My manager takes credit by getting work assigned to him/her done by his/her subordinates	.861
Innovative ideas and processes are discouraged by my manger as preserving the organisation's existing way of doing work is highly valued	.850
After my manager assumed duties in his/her job position well performed colleagues left the firm to join competing firms	.832
My manager became overly stressed, mentally disturbed or frequently sick even though he/she does not execute much productive work	.782
My manager may not successful in obtaining further promotions based on his/her performance in the current position	.739
Explained variation	72.36
Eigenvalue	7.05
Cronbach's alpha	.933

Table 2. Summary of results: factor analysis – HRM practices

	Factor loading			
	F1: Job description	F2: Promotion practices	F3: HRD interventions	F4: Performance management
My organisation maintains proper job descriptions for all job positions	.763			
My current job description has been clearly communicated to me	.792			
The work that I perform matches with my job description	.759			
My organisation uses job descriptions when selecting personnel for promotions		.748		
Promotion practices are well structured to identify the best candidates		.829		
Members of promotion panels in my organisation make impartial promotion decisions		.701		
My organisation gives due attention to individual's capabilities in making promotion decisions		.724		
My organisation provides job related skills/knowledge enhancement opportunities on technical matters			.712	
My organisation provides skills/knowledge enhancement opportunities on soft skill areas			.753	
My organisation has a standard method of HR development /talent management			.725	
I am happy with the opportunities I had for my development			.799	
My organisation has a standard method of evaluating employee performance				.751
I am happy with the current performance evaluation method				.723
Explained variation	36.82	24.87	11.31	7.01
Eigen-value	4.54	3.21	1.83	1.39
Cronbach's alpha	.846	.895	.924	.880

Table 3: Correlations

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1 Position tenure	1								
2 Age	.019	1							
3 Sex	.046	.099	1						
4 Education ^a	.039	.116	.014	1					
5 No. of employees ^b	.079	.017	.133	.102	1				
6 Performance management	.001	.108	.003	.098	.128	1			
7 Job description	.011	.016	.003	.170	.139*	.108	1		
8 HRD interventions	.002	.119	.104	.098	.102	.226*	.262*	1	
9 Promotion practices	.083	.114	.004	.105	.153*	.286*	.187*	.247*	1
10 Post-promotion performance	.085	.095	.023	.130	.122	.351**	.458**	.389**	.298**

Notes: ** significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), * significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). ^a Binary-coded variable, ^b Log transformed.

Table 4. Summary of results – parameter estimates

	Estimate	Wald
Position tenure	.136	.021
Age	.128	.027
Sex	.099	.090
Education	.153	.072
No. of employees	.546	.619
Performance management	1.002**	10.241
Job description	1.103***	16.131
HRD interventions	.777*	7.649
Promotion practices	1.028***	12.943

Notes: *** p<.001, ** p<.01.

Figures

Figure 1. ROC curve

Appendix

Appendix 1. Collinearity tests for predictors

Predictor	Tests of equality of group means (<i>F</i>)	Standardized canonical discriminant function coefficients	Structure Matrix
Job description	245.316	.581	.895
Promotion practices	230.125	.509	.867
Performance management	146.984	.043	.693
HRD interventions	144.204	.014	.686

Appendix 2. Estimates of area under the curve

Test Result Variable(s)	Area	Std. Error	Asymptotic Sig.	Asymptotic 95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Job description	.871	.020	.000	.831	.910
Promotion practices	.858	.020	.000	.819	.898
Performance management	.825	.022	.000	.781	.868
HRD interventions	.815	.023	.000	.771	.860